

Research Article

The Impact of Staff Training on Project Implementation in Somali Aid Foundation (SAF), Mogadishu, Somalia

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Abstract

The study sought to determine how staff training affected the way projects were carried out at the Somali Aid Foundation (SAF), located in Mogadishu, Somalia.

In order to determine the impact of project execution on employee training at Somali Aid Foundation (SAF), Mogadishu, Somalia, the study's goals were to examine the organization's staff training practices, evaluate the level of project execution there, and compare the two.

To determine the effect of staff training on project implementation at the Somali Aid Foundation (SAF), the study used a descriptive research methodology. The impacts of the variables under investigation were examined by the researcher using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

The Somali Aid Foundation (SAF) in Mogadishu had poor project implementation, according to the report. This further implies that after training its project team, SAF management must work harder to enhance the scope of project implementation.

According to the study's conclusion, training helps organizations identify when their employees are not performing up to par and adjust their knowledge, abilities, and attitudes to meet the needs of the company.

According to the report, this procedure need to be required for both new hires and those who advance in their careers.

Keywords: *Staff Training, Project Implementation, Project Manager, Employee promotion.*

INTRODUCTION

Practitioners, scholars, and legislators have attempted to identify and assess specific workplace procedures and systems of procedures that can increase employees' productivity and competitiveness since the start of the industrial revolution. Initiatives referred to as flexible work organizations, employee involvement, employee participation, or high-performance practices have received more attention recently. (Bobson, 2003).

There is conflicting empirical data to support the assertion made by proponents of these techniques that they boost productivity. To assess these practices now, it can be helpful to look at examples of comparable methods used in the past. (Mackinson, 2001).

Staff training and development, according to Mccoy (2004), refers to the official and informal, ongoing initiatives of organizations to enhance the performance and self-fulfillment of their employees through a range of strategies and initiatives.

These initiatives have found many uses in the contemporary workplace, ranging from long-term professional development to training in extremely specialized job abilities. Training and development has become a recognized profession with unique ideas and methods, a formal company function, and an essential component of strategy in recent years. In order to foster employee development and acquire a highly qualified workforce, an increasing number of businesses of all sizes have used both on-the-job and off-job training approaches. (Mullen, 2010).

Employees must be removed from their regular work contexts for training, so they are unable to focus fully.

However, as detailed below, examples of off-the-job training include conferences, role-playing, and many more.

The Somali Aid Foundation (SAF) has made an effort to train its employees to perform better so that their initiatives can be carried out successfully.

Despite the fact that SAF has employed several training techniques, project implementation has decreased during the last three years (2020–2023).

The majority of the authors mentioned have spoken more about project implementation and staff training in industrialized nations than in Africa, especially in Mogadishu, Somalia.

The article's goal is to clarify how staff training affects the way projects are carried out at the Somali Aid Foundation (SAF) in Mogadishu, Somalia.

Material and Methods

The research used This study examined the effect of staff training on project execution at the Somali Aid Foundation (SAF) in Mogadishu, Somalia, using a descriptive, qualitative, and quantitative research design.

A common method for describing and comprehending human behavior or experiences in relation to a certain phenomenon is qualitative research.

To determine the connection between staff training and project implementation at the Somali Aid Foundation (SAF), qualitative research uses subjective data that is challenging to code.

Mugenda and Mugenda (2003) concur that the design is the most favoured since it provides a report on things as they truly are, and Ghauri and Gronhaug (2005) claim that employing descriptive makes the problem structured and clearly understood.

Ethical Consideration

To conduct this study, the researchers were behaved ethically and confidentially, thus, the researchers were kept any privacy, confidentiality and secrecy of respondents, and were exclusively used for the purpose academic and as the respondents were informed about of the contents and the aims of the research prior to administering of any instrument.

Interpretation and Analysis of Data

The respondents' distribution across the four criteria of gender, age, educational background, and work experience is displayed in the table below. Analysis was done using percentages and frequency tables.

Results

Table 4. 1: Demographic Characteristics of Study Respondents

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	68	68%
Female	32	32%
Total	100	100%
Age Distribution		
Below 25 years	12	12%
26 – 30 years	15	15%
31 – 35 years	21	21%
36 – 40 years	18	18%
>40years	34	34%
Total	100	100%
Educational Qualification		
Secondary	16	16%
Certificate	11	11%
Diploma	25	25%

Degree	35	35%
Master	13	13%
Total	100	100%
Work Experience		
<1 year	8	8%
1 – 2 years	15	15%
3 – 4 years	33	33%
5 – 6 years	26	26%
>6 years	20	20%
Total	100	100%

Source: Primary Data, 2023

It should be mentioned that the respondents' age distribution was skewed towards their muscularity. In percentage terms, of the 100 respondents who took part in the survey, 68% were men and 32% were women. This indicates that men made up the majority of the project staff. This suggests that the SAF's recruitment practices were skewed towards being more macho.

Regarding the respondents' age distribution, it was discovered that those 40 years of age and above made up the largest percentage of the sample (34%). The age group of 31 to 35 years old, which made up 21% of this group, came next. The third group, which made up 18% of the 100 respondents, was those aged 36 to 40. The group of responders aged 26 to 30 with a 15% composition came next. With a composition of only 12%, the age group under 25 had the lowest percentage of composition.

This data unequivocally demonstrates that the Somali Aid Foundation (SAF), Mogadishu, had a higher proportion of old individuals in the under-25 age range, accounting for only 12% of the total population. This resulted from cultural perceptions that older persons are more adept at project management and, therefore, more successful at executing projects. The majority of Somali Aid Foundation (SAF) employees held bachelor's degrees as their highest level of education, according to the organization's educational standards.

These 35 respondents made up 35% of the total number of respondents included in the study. The diploma holders then came next with a composition of 25%. Secondary school certificates accounted for 16% of the third category of educational qualifications. Those with master's degrees came next with 13% of the composition.

Lastly, the group of responders who had certificates as their highest qualification comprised the final category. According to this analysis, the staff members had sufficient education and could therefore manage project-related tasks. The respondents' job experience at the Somali Aid Foundation (SAF) was the final factor examined under the demographic traits and profile of the respondents.

The majority of respondents (32% composition) had between three and four years of job experience, according to the findings.

Twenty percent of the 100 respondents fell into the third category under job experience, which was occupied by respondents with six years or more of experience. 15% of the composition was made up of people with 1-2 years of work experience, while 8% was made up of people with less than 1 year.

According to this data, the employees possessed sufficient experience to work for the Somali Aid Foundation (SAF). Since few employees were new to the company and many had been there for more than three years, it also indicates that employee turnover was minimal.

Examining the staff training practices of the Somali Aid Foundation (SAF), located in Mogadishu, Somalia, was the study's primary goal.

This was crucial in helping the researcher determine whether staff training methods were better than those used by the Somali Aid Foundation's (SAF) administration.

The t statistic, means, standard deviation, and ranks were employed in the analysis of this goal. In addition to the data from the closed-ended surveys, qualitative data was also examined. The analysis produced the following findings. The data relevant to the responses regarding the staff training procedures of the Somali Aid Foundation (SAF), located in Mogadishu, Somalia, is tabulated in the accompanying table.

Table4.2: to investigate the staff training methods of Somali Aid Foundation (SAF), Mogadishu, Somalia

Statements	Mean	Std.Dev	Interpret	Rank
Orientation is done for our employees within our organisation	1.93	1.402	Low	1
We do apprenticeship of employees to improve their skills	1.83	1.262	Low	2
Simulation training is done at our organisation to aid employees' with exposure	1.22	1.096	Very Low	5
Instructors who conduct inductions and orientations and well knowledgeable about work environment issues	1.79	1.044	Very Low	3
Our organisation has the required facilities for conducting on the job training	1.46	1.004	Very Low	4
Average Mean	1.65		Very Low	

The respondents' responses to the statement, "Orientation is done for our employees within our local government," were the category's highest indicator variable. With a mean of 1.93, this indicator variable was considered low. The statement "Simulation training is done at our organization to aid employees' with exposure" had the lowest indicator variable in this category, with a mean score of 1.22, which is considered very poor.

This indicates that the Somali Aid Foundation (SAF) training was not only badly conducted but also unappreciated by the participants and staff as a whole. This further demonstrates how the staff members underestimate the effectiveness of this training approach. The Somali Aid Foundation (SAF),

Mogadishu, has an average mean staff training practice of 1.65, which is very low and suggests that not much has been done to train SAF staff.

According to McCoy (2004), staff training and development refers to the ongoing, formal and informal initiatives taken by organisations to enhance the performance and self-fulfilment of their workforce through a range of initiatives and programs. These initiatives have found many uses in the contemporary workplace, ranging from long-term professional development to training in extremely specialised job abilities. Examining the degree of project implementation at the Somali Aid Foundation (SAF), located in Mogadishu, Somalia, was the second goal. The outcomes are shown below. The outcomes of calculating the means, standard deviation, and t statistic following analysis are shown in the table below.

Table 4.3: to assess the degree of project execution in Somali Aid Foundation (SAF), Mogadishu, Somalia

This construct variable had an overall mean of 2.02, which was considered low. This indicates that the

Statements	Mean	St. Dev	Interpret	Rank
The implementation of projects in sustainable sanitation and water management is complex	2.14	1.209	Low	4
Project implementation requires the coordination of a wide range of activities, diverse institutional arrangements, and different time frames	2.88	1.224	None	1
There is not one typical project in water and sanitation, as the actions may vary from the construction of a new infrastructure	2.57	1.124	Low	2
Most projects implemented cover issues such as: social development, health, environmental sustainability	1.95	1.129	Very Low	5
It is important to take into account that independently of the nature of the project, implementation takes time	2.55	1.024	Low	3
Average Mean	2.42		LOW	

Somali Aid Foundation (SAF), located in Mogadishu, Somalia, implemented the project to a minimal degree.

With a mean of 2.88, this indicator variable was considered low. The statement that "Most projects implemented cover issues such as: social development, health, environmental sustainability" has the lowest indicator variable in this category. With a mean score of 1.95, this statement was considered extremely low.

This is consistent with DFID's (2013) observation that programs pertaining to sustainable sanitation and water management are difficult to implement.

It necessitates coordinating a variety of operations across various time periods and institutional configurations. There isn't a single typical project in water and sanitation because the activities might range from building new infrastructure to implementing innovative methods of operation.

Social development, health, environmental sustainability, institutional strengthening, technical implementation, pilot plants, service delivery, social marketing, hygiene promotion, sanitation promotion, and capacity building are some of the topics covered by projects in this field.

Table 4. 4: establish the effects of project execution on employee training in Somali Aid Foundation (SAF), Mogadishu, Somalia.

Statements	Mean	S.D	Interpret	Rank
Trained employees in the organization are quicker and more effective in executing their activities	1.35	1.044	Very Low	3
Highly trained staff are responsive enough to directives from above	1.55	1.004	Very Low	2
Trained staff are generally sensitive to the needs of the public and react quickly to them	1.72	1.002	Very Low	1
Highly trained staff treasure quality and effectiveness in their operations	1.21	0.987	Very Low	4
Employees understand the relevance of responsiveness in their undertakings	1.11	0.789	Very Low	5
Average mean	1.39		Very Low	

Source: Primary Data, 2023

This construct variable had an overall mean of 1.39, which was considered extremely low. The claim that "Trained staff are generally sensitive to the needs of the public and react quickly to them" had the highest indicator variable in this category. The mean for this statement was determined to be 1.72, which was considered extremely low.

The assertion that "Employees understand the relevance of responsiveness in their undertakings" incurred had the lowest indicator variable under this category, with a mean score of 1.11, which is considered very low.

This indicates that the staff members were quite slow in providing their services to customers. It was discovered from the interviews that the majority of respondents did not accept this and instead praised the SAF staff for their quick service.

There is still more work to be done to train the project staff on how to carry out their tasks, as the average mean of 1.39 indicated a relatively poor relationship. Additionally, when workers are so well-trained that they can directly experience the joy that comes from a sense of accomplishment and the

knowledge that they are growing their innate abilities, discontent complaints, absenteeism, and turnover can be significantly decreased.

Discussions

The Somali Aid Foundation (SAF) in Mogadishu, Somalia, was found to have very low staff training procedures, which suggests that not much has been done to train SAF staff.

The Somali Aid Foundation (SAF) in Mogadishu was determined to have a low level of project implementation. This further implies that after training its project team, SAF management must work harder to enhance the scope of project implementation.

The response to the question, "Project implementation requires the coordination of a wide range of activities, diverse institutional arrangements, and different time frames," yielded the highest indicator variable in this category. With a mean of 2.88, this indicator variable was considered low.

The statement that "Most projects implemented cover issues such as: social development, health, environmental sustainability" has the lowest indicator variable in this category.

With a mean score of 1.95, this statement was considered extremely low. The main goal of this research study was to determine the impact of project execution and personnel training at the Somali Aid Foundation (SAF), located in Mogadishu, Somalia. This construct variable had an overall mean of 1.39, which was considered extremely low.

The claim that "Trained staff are generally sensitive to the needs of the public and react quickly to them" had the highest indicator variable in this category. The mean for this statement was determined to be 1.72, which was considered extremely low. The assertion that "Employees understand the relevance of responsiveness in their undertakings" incurred had the lowest indicator variable under this category, with a mean score of 1.35, which is considered very low. This indicates that the staff members had significant delays in providing their services to customers.

Conclusion

On-the-job training is still extensively used today, according to the study's findings. In actuality, it is arguably the most often used training approach since it simply needs a person who is proficient in the work and the equipment they employ to complete it.

Because no specialised equipment is required beyond what is typically utilized on the work, it is frequently affordable. On the other hand, the study finds that the execution of projects in sustainable sanitation and water management is complicated because on-the-job training removes the trainer and materials from production for the duration of the training period.

It necessitates the coordination of numerous operations, several institutional setups, and various timelines. It is crucial to remember that, regardless of the project's nature, implementation takes time—typically longer than anticipated—and that a variety of outside factors may arise. These factors should be taken into account when starting the implementation phase. It's crucial to remember that this is insufficient and that workers must continuously adjust to new demands for job performance. To put it another way, companies must have ongoing training and retention programs in place rather than waiting for skill and performance gaps to arise.

Recommendations

This approach should be required for both new hires and those who are promoted to a higher position, according to the report. In reality, one should be orientated whenever they move from one description to another that they were unfamiliar with.

In addition to fostering professionalism, this will help to boost employee confidence, which is crucial for customer service agents and other staff members.

Employees must put up a lot of effort to attend workshops and seminars. These should be available to anybody who might want to access the training, not just members of a particular class.

Organizations should think about sending some of their employees back to school for additional education in addition to seminars and workshops that offer a temporary learning opportunity. Employee loyalty is ensured because it would be more difficult for them to abandon the company to which they have very strong ties.

Compliance with ethical standards (WJS-I-Heading no numbering)

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest related to this study

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study

References

- Bobson, D. (2003). *Aspects of Customer Care and Service*. London: Queen's Tower Publishing Company Ltd, London, Wayward Street.
- Ghauri PN, Grønhaug K (2005) *Research methods in business studies: a practical guide*, 3rd edn. Prentice Hall, Harlow, UK
- Mccoy, A. (2004). *Motivation in Work Places: Analysis of the Modern Work Place Employee*. Mississippi: Z-Com Brothers Publishers.
- Mullen, H. (2010). *Staff Training Procedures and Protocol*. Washington DC, USA: Printlog Publishing Network.
- Mackinson, J. (2001). *Hotels Orientation Programs and Benefits*. California: Leonards and the Nerds Base Publishers.
- Mugenda O.M., and Mugenda, A. G. (2003). *Research Methods. Quantitative & Qualitative Approaches*. Nairobi: Press African Center for Technology Studies (ACTS)